

Telephone Poll Poisoning via Mass Voice SIMs: Emerging Threats to Public Opinion Research

Hajime Tsui

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Abstract

While the use of SIM farms for social media manipulation and other influence operations is a well-documented phenomenon, this paper examines a different angle: the potential threat that mass-scale, voice-enabled SIM operations pose to traditional telephone-based public opinion research.

1. Potential Vulnerability in Public Opinion Research

Telephone polling often employs Random Digit Dialing (RDD). However, an adversary operating a vast network of voice-enabled SIM cards could systematically respond to these polling calls. By providing coordinated, biased responses, such actors can "poison" the dataset, intentionally undermining the integrity of the research.

2. Conclusion

Survey poisoning via mass SIM deployment represents a new "cyber-social" threat to the collective decision-making processes that depend on statistical reliability... maybe? Moving forward, polling organizations must implement more robust security measures to verify respondent authenticity and detect duplication.

3. Ethical Considerations

This paper intentionally omits detailed attack procedures and implementation specifics to prevent misuse.

Changelog

Version 1.1 (2026-03-01)

- Refined Conclusion

Version 1.2 (2026-04-01)

- Added a new section (Section 3): Ethical Considerations